

D4.2

Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

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Authors	Ferdinando Bosco (ENG), Pierluigi Linardi (ENG), Angelo Triveri (ENG), Guillaume Piccarreta (IRCAM), Hugues Vinet (IRCAM), Filisia Melissari (SYN), Aggelos Orfanoudakis (SYN), Nelly Leligou (INTRA), Francisco Moreno Garcia (UPM)
Reviewers	Konstantinidis Dimitrios (CERTH), Francesca Portante (KUL)

Abstract

This deliverable presents the design, implementation, integration and delivery of the DAFNE+ Platform.

Starting from the User Requirements, Technical Specification and Architecture provided in WP2, the DAFNE+ Platform and its own components was implemented and integrated.

This document mainly focuses on the Application Layer Components, Identity Management, Integration Layer as well as all the methodology aspects related to the development and integration of the other components.

In addition, here is reported how all the components developed in WP3 (Content Creation Tools) and in T4.1, T4.2 and T4.3 (Blockchain Real, NFT Tool and Marketplace) were also integrated in the first version of the DAFNE+ Platform.

Keywords

Creative Industry, Multi Application Platform, Blockchain, Identity Management

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			<p>Hugues Vinet (IRCAM)</p> <p>Filisia Melissari (SYN)</p> <p>Aggelos Orfanoudakis (SYN)</p> <p>Nelly Leligou (INTRA)</p> <p>Francisco Moreno Garcia (UPM)</p> <p>Ámbar Tenorio Fornés (FCF)</p>
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Disclaimer

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Table of contents

1	Executive summary.....	13
2	Introduction.....	14
2.1	Purpose and context of the document.....	14
2.2	Document structure.....	14
2.3	Dependencies to-from other WPs.....	15
3	DAFNE + Platform Design.....	16
3.1	Architecture and requirements.....	16
3.1.1	Application Layer.....	18
3.2	Methodology - Development, integration and deployment.....	19
3.2.1	Micro frontend Design.....	19
3.2.2	DAFNE+ Application Integration and Deployment.....	23
3.3	DAFNE+ Generic Business Processes.....	26
3.3.1	GBP 1 - Content Creation.....	26
3.3.2	GBP 2 - Contributors Management.....	28
3.3.3	GBP 3 - NFT creation.....	29
3.3.4	GBP 4 - NFT Content Analysis and Tagging.....	31
3.3.5	GBP5 - NFT sale and redistribution.....	32
4	Integration of 3rd party applications and tools.....	35

4.1	Integration Layer.....	35
4.1.1	Design.....	37
4.1.2	Architecture.....	37
4.2	Tools.....	39
4.2.1	NFTs.....	40
4.2.2	Art and Music.....	41
4.2.3	Social Media.....	42
4.2.4	Other sharing tools.....	43
4.3	APIs, interfaces and specifications.....	43
5	Identity and Profile Management.....	47
6	DAFNE+ Platform First Release – Implementation, components integration and deployment.....	51
6.1	DAFNE+ Platform – Master App and UI.....	51
6.2	DAFNE+ Applications.....	54
6.2.1	Content Management.....	54
6.2.2	Tools Catalogue.....	70
6.2.3	Supporting tools - FAQ and Chat.....	79
6.2.4	GIT and Version Management.....	83
6.3	Additional tools.....	86
6.3.1	Matomo.....	86

6.3.2	Discourse.....	86
6.4	Content Creation Tools.....	86
6.4.1	Object Reconstruction Tool Backend.....	87
6.4.2	3D Object Reconstruction Frontend.....	88
6.4.3	Pose estimation Tool Backend.....	89
6.4.4	3D Pose Estimation Frontend.....	90
6.4.5	Style transfer tool - Backend.....	92
6.4.6	Style transfer tool - UI.....	92
6.4.7	Virtual Avatar Personalization Frontend.....	93
6.5	DAFNE+ Platform First Release.....	94
7	Conclusion.....	96
8	References.....	97

List of figures

Figure 1: DAFNE+ Architecture.....	17
Figure 2: DAFNE+ Micro frontend Concept.....	22
Figure 3: Micro Frontend architecture [3].....	24
Figure 4: GBP1 - Content Creation sequence diagram.....	27
Figure 5: GBP2 - Contributor Management sequence diagram.....	29
Figure 6: GBP3 - NFT Creation sequence diagram.....	31
Figure 7: GBP4 - NFT Content analysis and tagging sequence diagram.....	32
Figure 8: GBP5 - NFT Sale and redistribution sequence diagram.....	34
Figure 9: Integration Layer workflow - Sequence Diagram.....	38
Figure 10: Integration Layer Architecture.....	39
Figure 11: Integration Layer APIs and Tools.....	44
Figure 12: Integration Layer APIs GUI.....	45
Figure 13: Integration Layer APIs Keycloak plugin.....	46
Figure 14: Identity Manager - Keycloak interface.....	48
Figure 15: DAFNE+ Identity Manager mechanisms.....	49
Figure 16: Extended User Profile.....	50
Figure 17: DAFNE+ Platform Login	52
Figure 18: DAFNE+ Platform Registration.....	52

Figure 19: DAFNE+ Platform User Profile.....	53
Figure 20: DAFNE+ Platform - Metamask integration.....	53
Figure 21: Organization, teams and projects schema.....	56
Figure 22: Content Management Tool Architecture.....	58
Figure 23: Content Management GUI - Content list.....	63
Figure 24: Content Management GUI - Import Content.....	64
Figure 25: Content Management GUI - Add/Edit Contributors.....	65
Figure 26: Content Management GUI - Metamask integration.....	65
Figure 27: Content Management GUI - Contributors list and revenue sharing.....	66
Figure 28: Content Management GUI - New Organization.....	66
Figure 29: Content Management GUI - Organization List.....	67
Figure 30: Content Management GUI - New Team.....	67
Figure 31: Content Management GUI - New Team Member.....	68
Figure 32: Content Management GUI - My Teams and Shared Contents.....	68
Figure 33: Tools Catalogue GUI - Tool List.....	75
Figure 34: Tools Catalogue GUI - Tool Detail.....	76
Figure 35: Tools Catalogue GUI - Tool documentation.....	77
Figure 36: Chat Plugin button - Discord Icon.....	82
Figure 37: Chat Plugin displayed.....	83

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

Figure 38: Example of Versions Display Interface in IRCAM Forum85

Figure 39: Test book template for user acceptance test.....95

List of tables

Table 1: DAFNE+ external APIs.....	35
Table 2: NFT Marketplaces.....	40
Table 3: Content Management Tool APIs.....	60
Table 4: Chat solutions comparison.....	80
Table 5: Style Transfer Tool environment variables.....	92

Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
CRUD	Create, Read, Update and Delete
FAQ	Frequently Asked Question
GBP	Generic Business Process
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IAM	Identity and Access Management
NFT	Non-Fungible Token
OS	Operating System
RAM	Random Access Memory
REST	Representational State Transfer
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
UI	User Interface
WP	Work Package

1 Executive summary

The DAFNE+ Platform aims to be a “collaborative content sharing platform for DAOs over blockchains, easing the participation of artists and creators in the business models generated thanks to DAFNE+ ecosystem”.

Starting from the collection of the user and system requirements, together with the technical specifications and architecture design, the first version of the DAFNE+ Platform was implemented and released to be validated by the end-users in the different pilot scenarios.

The DAFNE+ Platform is a multi-layer platform which integrates all the Content Creation Tools developed in WP3 as well as the Blockchain Realm and blockchain-based components implemented in T4.1, T4.2 and T4.3 and reported in D4.1, including NFT Marketplace.

In addition, the DAFNE+ Platform provides an Application Layer with UI-Based applications facilitating the Content Import and Management for the users as well as the definition of content sharing and revenue models.

All the UI-based applications were implemented adopting a micro-frontend approach, ensuring a decoupling of the implemented modules and facilitating the integration and deployment phase.

Finally, the DAFNE+ allows to integrate 3rd party applications through the Integration Layer and manages the identity and profiles of the users in a centralized way in order to provide recommended and personalized contents.

The first release of the DAFNE+ Platform was deployed in a public cloud infrastructure and made available to the end-users which are able to register to it and test it.

2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose and context of the document

This document reports the activities conducted in the tasks T4.4 and T4.5 in the first period of the project.

The main goal of this document is to describe the DAFNE+ Platform, including all the design, implementation and integration aspects, including the 3rd party integration.

The document provides an overview on the methodology used for design of the platform, in particular the micro frontend approach, starting from the DAFNE+ Architecture. It also includes the list of components integrated in the overall platforms with the description of specific architectural aspects, interfaces and specifications. Finally, the document describes the identity and profile management and how the 3rd party applications can be integrated through the Integration Layer.

2.2 Document structure

In addition to the Executive Summary and this introductory chapter, the document is structured into 5 additional chapters:

- Chapter 3 introduces the design aspects of the DAFNE+ Platform, including the methodology and the business process implemented and to be evaluated in the first version of the platform.
- Chapter 4 describes the Integration Layer components, which are in charge of integrating all the 3rd party applications and exposing the Content Creation Tools outside of the DAFNE+ ecosystem using standardized APIs.
- Chapter 5 describes the Identity and Profile Management Tool and the related mechanisms for registration, authentication and authorization, shared among all the DAFNE+ components.
- Chapter 6 described the actual release of the first version of DAFNE+ Platform, including all the components implemented and integrated in WP4 as well as description about deployment and integration of the Content Creation Tool, implemented in WP3.

- Chapter 7 concludes this document.

2.3 Dependencies to-from other WPs

The main inputs for the implementation, integration, and release of the DAFNE+ Platform were the outcomes provided in WP2, including the Requirements and DAFNE+ Architecture. In addition, the technical specification of Content Creation Tools, provided by WP3, were fundamental for the integration phase.

The methodology for the implementation of the UI components was applied in WP3 for the implementation of the UI of the Content Creation Tools and the first release of the DAFNE+ Platform will be exploited in WP5 for the evaluation phase within the different scenarios.

3 DAFNE + Platform Design

The Design phase of the DAFNE+ Platform started in WP2, where user and technical requirements were collected for defining the DAFNE+ Architecture and Technical Specifications.

3.1 Architecture and requirements

Following the DAFNE+ Architecture, the DAFNE+ Platform is a multi-layer platform in which many components collaborate with each other for implementing an overall ecosystem in which the end-user is able to collaborate and share content, defining innovative business models and revenue mechanisms.

Figure 1 below represents from a visual perspective all the layers and components expected to be part of DAFNE+ ecosystem.

FIGURE 1: DAFNE+ ARCHITECTURE

The DAFNE + Platform integrates several layer and components in an overall system. Among these, those implemented in the context of WP4 and specifically in tasks T4.4. and T4.5 are:

- Application Layer, it consists of all the end-user applications.
- Identity Management, it provides user registration and login as well as authorization on resource access.
- Integration Layer, it allows developers to integrate essential DAFNE+ functionalities and provides a toolset that allows users to integrate DAFNE+ contents in third-party platforms.

All these components and applications are described more in details in Ch.4, Ch.5 and Ch.6.

3.1.1 Application Layer

The Application Layer is the top layer of the DAFNE+ Architecture and consists of several end-user applications, made available through the DAFNE+ Platform User Interface.

In the first version of the DAFNE+ Platform the following applications are available:

- Content Management
- NFT Marketplace
- Tools UIs
- Tools Catalogue
- Supporting Applications (Chat and FAQ)

Each application consists of the backend part, which contains the business logic and the interfaces with the other layers and components of DAFNE+ platform, as well as the frontend part, which will provide easy access to the end-users.

The applications included in the Application Layer are able to interact with the Blockchain Realm, with the DAFNE+ toolset as well as with the Storage Layer, for the data management and storage and the Integration Layer, for external integrations.

More details on the DAFNE+ Application are reported in Ch. 6.1 and in D4.1 (NFT Marketplace).

For the development of the end-user application, a specific methodology was followed in order to create a harmonic ecosystem that facilitates the user experience, as well as for facilitating the integration and deployment phase.

3.2 Methodology - Development, integration and deployment

As already described in the previous paragraph, the DAFNE+ Platform consists of several layers and applications, and among those, the most important is the one to provide a GUI to end users, to make the most of the potential offered by the platform.

The development of DAFNE+ Platform applications is entrusted to multiple teams, partners of the consortium, that need to work independently for implementing and releasing specific features of the platform itself.

In order to facilitate the development, integration and deployment phase a specific methodology was identified: Micro frontend approach.

3.2.1 Micro frontend Design

The Micro frontend architectural approach consists of techniques, strategies and recipes for building modern web apps with multiple teams that can ship features independently [1].

Micro frontend web applications are built on a decentralized way. Just like microservices break down the backend of an application into smaller, independently deployable services, micro frontends aim to break down the frontend into smaller, self-contained modules. Each module, often referred to as a micro frontend, represents a distinct part of the user interface and can be developed, tested, and deployed independently of the others.

The main characteristics and principles of micro frontends include [1]:

- **Be Technology Agnostic**

Each team should be able to choose and upgrade their stack without having to coordinate with other

teams. Custom Elements are a great way to hide implementation details while providing a neutral interface to others.

- **Isolate Team Code**

Don't share a runtime, even if all teams use the same framework. Build independent apps that are self-contained. Don't rely on shared state or global variables.

- **Establish Team Prefixes**

Agree on naming conventions where isolation is not possible yet. Namespace CSS, Events, Local Storage and Cookies to avoid collisions and clarify ownership.

- **Favor Native Browser Features over Custom APIs**

Use Browser Events for communication instead of building a global PubSub system. If you really must build a cross-team API, try keeping it as simple as possible.

- **Build a Resilient Site**

Your feature should be useful, even if JavaScript failed or hasn't executed yet. Use Universal Rendering and Progressive Enhancement to improve perceived performance.

Micro frontends are therefore an architectural pattern that applies the decoupling logic of microservices to the frontend part.

Among the many benefits we find:

- Greater scalability, because individual parts can scale independently.
- Development speed and agility: teams work and release their portions of code independently.
- Independence in development, which translates into the possibility not only of developing different parts at the same time, but also of adding, removing or rewriting parts of the frontend without this affecting its stability or functioning.

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

- Reduction of time to market for new digital services.
- Smaller and therefore manageable codebase.
- Possibility of using different frameworks within the same application.

3.2.1.1 Micro Frontend in DAFNE+ - Master and Sub-App

The micro frontend approach was implemented for integrating all the Frontend Application into the main DAFNE+ Platform.

The main DAFNE+ Platform can be considered the “Master App” and includes Login, User Profile, Sidebar, Header and Footer.

All the others frontend applications can be considered “Sub-Apps” and are loaded time-by-time in the container of the Master App, based on the end-user selection.

In the first version of the DAFNE+ Platform the list of the Frontend applications includes:

- Content Management
- NFT Marketplace
- Tools UI
- Tools Catalogue
- FAQ & Chat

The Figure 2 below, shows a conceptual schema of the Master and Sub App.

FIGURE 2: DAFNE+ MICRO FRONTEND CONCEPT

Common technologies and techniques used in micro frontend development include Single SPA, Module Federation (a feature in Webpack 5), and custom routing and orchestration solutions.

Based on the needs and specification of the DAFNE+ Platform, the Webpack Module Federation [2] was selected for building the DAFNE applications.

3.2.1.2 Module Federation

In the Module Federation approach, multiple separate builds form a single application. These separate builds act like containers and can expose and consume code between builds, creating a single, unified application.

The Module Federation support the integration of local and remote modules. Local modules are regular modules that are part of the current build. Remote modules are modules that are not part of the current build but are loaded at runtime from a remote container.

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

Thanks to the Webpack Module Federation:

- It is possible to expose and consume any module type that webpack supports.
- Chunk loading should load everything needed in parallel.
- Control from consumer to container
 - Overriding modules is a one-directional operation.
 - Sibling containers cannot override each other's modules.
- Concept is environment independent.
 - Usable in web, Node.js, etc.

3.2.2 DAFNE+ Application Integration and Deployment

The DAFNE+ Applications developed as Micro Frontend need to be integrated with their own backend as well as with other applications.

Following the microservices approach each Micro Frontend App communicate with its own backend in a full stack architecture, decoupling any services. Figure 3 shows a typical Micro Frontend Application with the backend services.

FIGURE 3: MICRO FRONTEND ARCHITECTURE [3]

3.2.2.1 Integration

In order to communicate with other services or apps each Micro Frontend app is able to access the storage data provided by the Master App and interact with other applications using REST APIs.

In addition, for ensuring the decoupling of the applications, the Master App also offers a series of shared services and information that can be accessed through specific browser events that can be used by applications to send the events or register to them.

In order to follow the Micro Frontend approach and facilitate the integration, some specifications were identified for the development of the DAFNE+ Applications:

- Frontend is developed as Micro Frontend application and must include:
 - Webpack v5.0
 - webpack.config.js with *ModuleFederationPlugin*
 - index.js with mount function
- Multi Framework is supported (e.g., Vuels + REACT)
- Expose REST APIs for the interaction (documented in OpenAPI standard [4])
- Use Identity Manager and Oauth2.0 [5] server for authorization mechanisms.
- No data exchange among Frontend Apps (only storage data or events)
- All needed data are retrieved via APIs.
- Frontend App must be exposed as standalone app in a web server.

3.2.2.2 Deployment

For facilitating software integration and deployment the containerization approach was followed. Containers offer advantages in terms of isolation, portability, consistency, efficiency, scalability, dependency management, version control, security, and automation.

Docker [6] and Docker Compose [7] are two essential tools that have revolutionized the way for packaging and deploying software applications. They provide a standardized, efficient, and reliable way to package, distribute, and manage applications, making it easier to work with microservices architectures, cloud-native applications, and containerized workloads.

For this reason, DAFNE+ Application release must follow the following specifications:

- All the applications must be packaged as docker containers.
- Frontend and Backend must be packaged separately (configuration can be defined in docker-compose files)
- Docker containers must be publicly available and configuration files published on the shared Git REPO
- All the application must include README file and documented APIs for describing the integration and deployment process.

3.3 DAFNE+ Generic Business Processes

The DAFNE+ Platform implements a series of Generic Business Processes (GBPs) that represent general purpose processes and functionalities offered by the DAFNE+ Platform applicable to any specific scenario described in D2.2 and to be validated in WP5 activities.

Any of this GBP can be adapted and/or extended for implementing the specific scenarios ensuring a minimum of functionalities exploitable in the different contexts and use cases.

3.3.1 GBP1 - Content Creation

One of the main goals of the DAFNE+ Platform is to allow the creators the creation of contents using any of the Content Creation Tool.

Any content created through the Content Creation Tools UI (navigating the DAFNE+ Platform) can be downloaded to the users file system or imported in the DAFNE+ Content Manager.

Importing the content within the Content Manager, an important processing step is required: the creation of a Smart Contract linked to the content itself.

The Smart Contract created for each content ensure the ownership and the traceability of the content as well as the possibility to define specific revenue sharing mechanisms.

This step is fundamental exploring additional features provided by the Content Manager and other DAFNE+ Applications.

The Figure 4 below shows the sequence diagram of the GBP1.

FIGURE 4: GBP1 - CONTENT CREATION SEQUENCE DIAGRAM

3.3.2 GBP2 - Contributors Management

In case a content was imported in the Content Manager (GBP1 – Content Creation), the Creator is able to:

- Retrieve its own imported contents (a list of contents).
- Access the detail of the contents and edit metadata.
- Manage the content revenue sharing models.

This last feature is linked to the Blockchain Realm. In fact, exploiting the smart contract associated to each content, is possible to define revenue sharing model (e.g., percentage of revenues for each contributor), register it to the blockchain and apply the self-execution of the revenue sharing when a content was sold.

Figure 5 below shows the sequence diagram of the GBP2.

FIGURE 5: GBP2 - CONTRIBUTOR MANAGEMENT SEQUENCE DIAGRAM

3.3.3 GBP3 - NFT creation

The NFT Marketplace allows the Creators to create NFT and publish it into the marketplace. A NFT can be created starting from a content imported in the Content Manager (GBP1 – Content Creation) or starting from items that already exists in other locations.

In both cases, the NFT is published on the marketplace via the Blockchain Realm and the NFT Tool, but only in the first case it will be possible to activate the automatic revenue redistribution mechanisms (GBP5 - NFT sale and redistribution).

Figure 6 below shows the sequence diagram of the GBP3.

⋮

FIGURE 6: GBP3 - NFT CREATION SEQUENCE DIAGRAM

3.3.4 GBP4 - NFT Content Analysis and Tagging

The GBP4 describes the creation of an NFT in the DAFNE+ marketplace, employing the NFT content analysis tool.

First, the Creator starts to create the NFT on the marketplace frontend (GBP3). He/she inserts the details of the NFT that are described in D4.1. Among the details and depending on the type of the item he/she wishes to create, he/she inserts the relative source of the NFT. The source can be for example an image of an artwork, or a video. Then, the Marketplace passes the source to the NFT content analysis tool that analyses

the source, understanding its type and content and produces a list of relevant attributes. These attributes are then passed to the user in the form of proposed tags they could select to tag their NFT with on the DAFNE+ Marketplace. The Creator presses the button to create the NFT, at which point the details are sent to the Blockchain Realm, where the metadata of the NFT are created and published on a decentralised storage, namely IPFS, and the NFT contract is created. The relative transaction object is sent back to the marketplace and the NFT is minted to the user's wallet. The above sequence is described in more detail in D4.1.

Figure 7 below shows the sequence diagram of the BP4.

FIGURE 7: GBP4 – NFT CONTENT ANALYSIS AND TAGGING SEQUENCE DIAGRAM

3.3.5 GBP5 - NFT sale and redistribution

The GBP5 describes what happens when a NFT is sale on the NFT Marketplace.

A registered user of the DAFNE+ Platform (a Buyer) can navigate into the NFT Marketplace and select a NFT to buy.

If the NFT is not linked to any content on the DAFNE+ Platform (via Content Manager) only the NFT ownership is changed. Otherwise, a complex process automatically starts involving the Content Manager and the Blockchain Realm.

In detail:

- The ownership of the content is updated in the Content Manager
- The revenues are shared among all the contributors.
- A new Smart Contract for the content is created for ensuring the DAFNE+ functionalities to the new Content Owner.

In addition, the distribute revenue function will distribute the price of the NFT among the contributors and will take a fee for the platform maintenance and DAO purposes. This fee will depend on the NFT price, being small for cheaper NFTs and larger for expensive purchases. Fees will be from 0.1% to 10% of the price.

DAFNE+ community will decide how to invest the money obtained from fees discussing proposals in the forum and chat and voting in the DAO. This feature will be available in future versions of the platform.

DAOs mechanism are not implemented in the first release of the DAFNE+ Platform and will be better elaborated in the next version of this deliverable (D4.4).

Figure 8 below shows the sequence diagram of the GBP5.

FIGURE 8: GBP5 - NFT SALE AND REDISTRIBUTION SEQUENCE DIAGRAM

4 Integration of 3rd party applications and tools

4.1 Integration Layer

The role of the integration layer component is twofold; first, it allows developers to integrate some essential DAFNE+ functionalities during the production process of their own projects, and second, it provides a toolset that allows users to use DAFNE+ content in third-party platforms. The integration layer is an essential component that ensures the sustainability of the DAFNE+ platform. A large percentage of the prospective DAFNE+ users are creators who, according to data collected during the user requirements collection phase, already have their own toolsets integrated in their workflows. Therefore, it's important that they are provided with the ability to use DAFNE+ as an integrated part of their already defined processes. Furthermore, according to the feedback gathered by the users, many creators have the need to advertise their works in popular platforms. Providing them paths for sharing the content they create in DAFNE+ to external platforms is therefore important to them.

APIs

DAFNE+ will provide a list of DAFNE+ services as APIs that external developers can consume to integrate DAFNE+ to their own projects. Towards this purpose, first a form was distributed between the component owners of the creative tools of DAFNE+, to figure out which tools could expose an API.

An initial list was gathered as depicted in the Table 1 below.

TABLE 1: DAFNE+ EXTERNAL APIS

Tool	API (Y/N)	Already existing	Support needed	Resp. Partner
------	-----------	------------------	----------------	---------------

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

Automatic Art Generator	Y	No	No	SYN
Style Transfer	Y	No	No	SYN
NFT Content Analysis	Y	Yes	No	UPM
3D Object Reconstruction	N	No	No	CERTH
3D Human Pose Estimation	N	No	No	CERTH
Virtual Avatar Personalisation	N	No	No	CERTH
WebPD	Y	No	Yes	IRCAM
Rave and nn	N	Yes	No	IRCAM
Dicy2	N	Yes	No	IRCAM
Rave v2 and v3	N	No	No	IRCAM
Spat	N	Yes	No	IRCAM
Soundworks	N	Yes	No	IRCAM
CoMo	N	Yes	No	IRCAM

Highlighted in green is the consolidated list of creative tools that will allow integration with third parties.

4.1.1 Design

For developers to consume these APIs, first they will need to connect to a DAFNE+ account, which they will use in order to gain access to the services. Then they will need to visit the DAFNE+ platform to find the detailed specifications of the provided endpoints. Considering the needs from the Integration Layer according to the workflow described above, the Kong API Gateway [8] was selected, as a solution to provide a unique entry point to the DAFNE+ services to the developers. API Gateways are tools to manage APIs in a centralised way. They provide a unique entry point to an array of services, acting as a reverse proxy, routing user requests to the appropriate services. Kong is an open-source API gateway tool. It provides a spectrum of features and functionalities for ensuring the security and managing APIs and microservices. Specifically, the features that are interesting to the DAFNE+ use case are:

- It provides a central point from where external developers can access the DAFNE+ services.
- It is highly scalable and can handle many requests.
- It offers a variety of plugins for:
 - Traffic control
 - Authentication and authorisation
 - Security
 - Logging and monitoring
- It offers the ability to create custom plugins.

Kong enables DAFNE+ to establish a unified access point for its services, streamlining authentication and authorization at the integration layer rather than at the individual service level. This approach enhances the solution’s manageability and scalability, making it more efficient and sustainable.

4.1.2 Architecture

For the purposes of DAFNE+, a custom plugin has been implemented using the Go scripting language and implementing authentication and authorisation functionality using the Identity and Profile Management component of DAFNE+. In Figure 9 the workflow of the custom plugin is depicted.

FIGURE 9: INTEGRATION LAYER WORKFLOW - SEQUENCE DIAGRAM

The developer will access their selected DAFNE+ service through the Integration layer API providing their DAFNE+ credentials. The integration layer through the Kong custom plugin, communicate with the Identity and Profile Management component to check whether the token is valid and active. If not, the user will be denied access to the DAFNE+ service. If the credentials are correct, the user’s request will be forwarded to the DAFNE+ service and the user will be able to use the service.

The overall architecture of the Integration Layer API is depicted in the Figure 10 below.

FIGURE 10: INTEGRATION LAYER ARCHITECTURE

The application layer of the API is based on Kong API Gateway, featuring a custom plugin built in GoLang [9]. The storage layer of the API is a PostgreSQL database. The component interfaces with the DAFNE+ services exposed to the external developers as outlined in section 4.3. Also, for usability reasons, the component features as well a GUI, based on an open-source tool, named Konga [10] that interprets the data of the Kong API Gateway.

4.2 Tools

Towards achieving integration of DAFNE+ with already existing 3rd party platforms, a series of tools will be provided. Taking into account the feedback gathered by the users during the requirements collection we considered popular platforms in three main categories:

1. NFTs
2. Art and Music
3. Social Media

Furthermore, tools allowing the sharing and exporting of the DAFNE+ content were also regarded under the context of the Integration Layer component.

4.2.1 NFTs

For the first category, we considered NFT related platforms, and specifically NFT marketplaces, with which we could integrate, thus allowing the users to list the DAFNE+ created NFTs there as well. We examined a series of renowned NFT marketplaces as depicted in the Table 2 below.

TABLE 2: NFT MARKETPLACES

Marketplace	Popularity (Sales Volume)	Asset Types
OpenSea	\$35.03B	Images, Audio, Video, 3D
LooksRare	\$4.85B	Images, Audio, Video
X2Y2	\$1.29B	Images, Audio, Video, 3D
Rarible	\$303.84M	Images, Audio Video
SuperRare	\$238.85M	Images, Video

Displayed are the NFT marketplaces that support at least the Ethereum blockchain. Popularity was measured according to the volume of sales since their existence, and the asset types specify the types of file formats that can be created as NFTs and displayed on each marketplace [11]. OpenSea was the final choice for the following reasons:

- The most popular platform according to the volume of sales
- The most preferred by the users (see D2.1)
- Supports both Ethereum and Polygon chains.
- Covers a wide variety of asset types that are also featured in DAFNE+

The integration of DAFNE+ with OpenSea happens on the level of the DAFNE+ marketplace. OpenSea offers a standard for NFT metadata in order to be able to display NFT information correctly. The structure of the NFT metadata, as described in D4.1 is carefully curated to be compliant with the OpenSea standard. Therefore, users are able to list DAFNE+ NFTs on OpenSea.

4.2.2 Art and Music

For the art and music category, we created an initial list of platforms by considering those platforms that users have stated they employ during their creation process or for advertising their creations. Afterwards, we investigated each platform according to the feasibility of integration, for example whether the platform provided an API, the compatibility with the context of DAFNE, and the existence or not of constraints, such as rate limits, and pricing. Below is the complete list of factors considered:

- Overall popularity
- Preference by DAFNE+ users
- Easiness/Feasibility of integration
- DAFNE+ use case compatibility/coverage

- Open source
- Free
- Constraints

Based on the criteria described, we selected SoundCloud. SoundCloud [12] is a widely used platform for discovering, streaming and sharing musical pieces. It allows artists, regardless of the level of experience, to share their music, be reimbursed fairly and reach a wide audience of fans.

This integration will happen at the level of music and sound content existing on DAFNE+. It can be potentially useful to almost half of the prospective users of DAFNE+ as reported in D2.1 in terms of users interested in the music and sound tools.

4.2.3 Social Media

For the final category examined, popular social media platforms were put into perspective. For this category as well, an initial list of platforms was created considering the user feedback and needs.

The evaluation criteria for this category follow the same logic as the previous category, outlined in section 4.2. While the user perspective is the primary focus and priority of DAFNE+, issues and constraints encountered during the examination of the platforms influenced the selection process heavily. For example, the social media platform most users choose to advertise their content is Instagram. Instagram is a social media app primarily focusing on visual content sharing, like images and videos. It features different types of profiles with different features, namely, personal, creator and business accounts, with the most common one being the personal type of account. At the time of writing, Instagram does not offer an API for sharing content on personal accounts, and therefore it cannot be supported by DAFNE+.

For this purpose, the social media channel supported by DAFNE+ will be LinkedIn [13], a professional social networking platform. The integration of DAFNE+ with LinkedIn will happen at the level of the NFT

marketplace. Specifically, users will have the option to share items on the marketplace on LinkedIn by visiting the item's page. Therefore, they will be able to reach a wider audience and at the same time attract more users on the DAFNE+ platform.

4.2.4 Other sharing tools

DAFNE+ will also support other functionalities for sharing and managing content as outlined below:

- Exporting assets in various formats
- Embedding options

As far as exporting is concerned, for new content created on the platform, the users will be given the choice to export the content in a list of supported formats. For instance, tools that create images, such as the Style Transfer tool, will enable users to download the image as either .jpg or .png. On the other hand, the 3D object reconstruction tool will enable users to download 3D objects as either .obj or .stl, each targeting different types of applications, such as game development and 3D printing.

As for the embedding options, this functionality will be related to items on the marketplace. Users will be given the option to copy a CSS snippet that will allow them to embed a marketplace item on websites. This way users can advertise their DAFNE+ assets on their personal blogs. This functionality will be implemented in a future version of the platform.

4.3 APIs, interfaces and specifications

The overall architecture of the Integration Layer component is depicted in Figure 11. The integration layer is interfacing with:

- a. The DAFNE+ services as outlined in section 4.1 and in general for implementing the abilities of the integration layer tools, as for example giving the users the functionality to export assets in various formats.
- b. The LinkedIn social platform.
- c. The Soundcloud platform.

FIGURE 11: INTEGRATION LAYER APIS AND TOOLS

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

The DAFNE+ Integration Layer API is provided to the users using the Swagger API Specification based on OpenAPI 3.0. The endpoints of the API and the related details are depended on the DAFNE+ services. More information about those can be found in D3.1 “Content production tools and recommendation engine (First version)”. The Integration Layer Tools are provided to the DAFNE+ services for integration, also using the Swagger API Specification. A more detailed view on those will be provided in the next version of the deliverable, as the current version focuses more on the Integration Layer API.

The Integration Layer is offered as two separate dockerised applications, one for the API and one for the tools. The API is configured using the details of the DAFNE+ services, as well as the details of the Identity and Profile Management component.

A view of the GUI used for the Integration Layer API is depicted in Figure 12.

FIGURE 12: INTEGRATION LAYER APIS GUI

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

Also, in Figure 13 highlighted is the custom plugin developed as “Keycloak” that can now be applied and secure any service added to the Integration Layer.

FIGURE 13: INTEGRATION LAYER APIs KEYCLOAK PLUGIN

5 Identity and Profile Management

Identity and access management provides control over user validation and resource access. This process, usually identified as IAM (Identity and Access Management) ensures that the right people, using a digital identity, access a specific digital resource at the right time and for the right reasons.

There are two main mechanisms included in the identity and access management:

- **Authentication**, the verification of a digital identity
- **Authorization**, the process of determining what resources a user can access.

The DAFNE+ Identity and Profile Management tool was implemented using Keycloak. Keycloak [14] is an open-source Identity and Access Management framework, which provides user authentication and fine-grained authorization, supporting the most used standards protocols such as OpenID, OAuth2.0 and SAML.

Keycloak also supports the role-based access management, single sign on and user federation. All the services and features can be managed via standardized APIs or a useful administration console. Figure 14 shows the Keycloak administration interface.

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

FIGURE 14: IDENTITY MANAGER - KEYCLOAK INTERFACE

The DAFNE+ Identity Management is able to:

- Register new users within the DAFNE+ Platform and allow the user login through UI and APIs (using username and password and obtaining secure tokens).
- Assign roles and permission to Client Applications and end-users, in order to allow the definition of user groups and roles, applying a role-based access control to the digital resources and applications.

The DAFNE+ Users can register and login directly from the DAFNE+ Platform, which is integrated with the Identity and Profile Management.

During the registration phase, specific information is requested from the user for creating an account and a User Profile on the Identity Management.

The login phase allows the User to access the DAFNE+ Platform and obtain a valid token that is used for navigating the UI (checked by all the DAFNE+ Applications) or for accessing APIs provided by the Integration Layer.

In fact, the DAFNE+ Platform allows the users to exploit the features offered by Content Creation Tools externally from the DAFNE+ UI. Additional information is provided in Ch.4.

The Identity Management is also in charge of checking and validating all the APIs provided by DAFNE+ Applications. For this reason, each DAFNE+ Application has its own credentials in the Identity Management and is able to interact with the other Applications using a valid OAuth2.0 token. In this way, the security of the APIs is ensured.

Figure 15 below shows a schema of authentication and authorization mechanisms within the DAFNE+ Identity Manager.

FIGURE 15: DAFNE+ IDENTITY MANAGER MECHANISMS

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

The Identity and Profiling Management tool also sets up and collects **User Profiles**. The User Profile on keycloak was extended for collecting and storing the key information to generate a structured User Profile and then visualizing the knowledge out of these findings. User profiling helps in personalising a system to work according to user preferences. The main application that exploits the extended User Profile is the AI Recommendation Engine for content filtering and personalization. More details on the AI Recommendation Engine are provided in D3.1.

In Figure 16 the additional fields of the extended user profile are listed.

FIGURE 16: EXTENDED USER PROFILE

6 DAFNE+ Platform First Release – Implementation, components integration and deployment

6.1 DAFNE+ Platform – Master App and UI

The DAFNE+ Platform UI is the Master App mentioned in Ch. 3.2.1.1. It consists of the main entry point to the DAFNE+ ecosystem including the main functionalities shared among all the other applications. More specifically, it provides:

- User Login, Registration and Profile Management
- Metamask Integration
- Session Storage and Event Dispatching

The Master App is the entry point for the end-users that are able to register and login, as well as to create and edit their own user profiles, integrating Keycloak APIs.

In addition, the Master App integrate the Metamask functionalities, exploiting the Metamask SDK, allowing to the interact with the Blockchain Realm and the Smart Contract functionalities.

Finally, thanks to the Webpack5 Module Federation and the Micro Frontend architecture, the Master App is able to manage the Sub-app and share the session storage with essential information (like user profile and session token) as well as managing the event dispatcher for the decoupled communication with other applications.

6.1.1.1 GUI sections

Login/Sign In

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

FIGURE 17: DAFNE+ PLATFORM LOGIN

FIGURE 18: DAFNE+ PLATFORM REGISTRATION

User Profile

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Profile

UserName: test-paris

Email: test@paris.it

First Name: Test

Last Name: Test

Country:

Type of user: Artist

Professionalism: Amateur

Interests:

Company:

Save

FIGURE 19: DAFNE+ PLATFORM USER PROFILE

Metamask Integration

FIGURE 20: DAFNE+ PLATFORM - METAMASK INTEGRATION

6.2 DAFNE+ Applications

In this chapter all the DAFNE+ Applications (included in the Application Layer) are described more in detail and for each Application the following information was reported:

- Overall description and main functionalities
- Architecture
- Specifications and Interface
- GUI sections
- Integration and Deployment
-

6.2.1 Content Management

As already described in D2.1 the Content Management tool is one of the Applications of the Dafne+ Platform.

It aims to implement a complete media asset management value chain: creation, management and distribution of the content. In addition, the Content Management tool allows to manage the contents in a hierarchical and collaborative way, implementing a structure of organizations, teams and projects that share the management of created content.

Creation

The creation of media assets within the DAFNE+ platform is intended as the possibility to import new content generated through the content creation tools of the DAFNE+ platform itself. The Content Management tool supports the most standard and relevant type of content, following the requirements expectations and needs. In addition, the Content Management Tool is also capable to manage content linked to external URI.

Management

In the first version of the Content Management Tool, the management phase covers some of the processes for the usage and the enrichment of the content within the DAFNE+ platform. The end-user has the possibility to:

- Edit metadata (title, description, additional info...)
- Add technical documentation
- Define contributors and revenue sharing percentage

Distribution

The first version of the Content Management implements the management and application of remuneration mechanisms in a redistributed way, integrating the Blockchain Realm and specific smart contracts for tracking the content creation, definition of contributors and automated revenue sharing.

Organizations, Teams, and Projects Management

In order to provide to the Creators a shared ecosystem, a basic Content Management structure was implemented. It is based on three-level hierarchal structure: Organizations, Teams and Projects.

The structure is shown in Figure 21.

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

FIGURE 21: ORGANIZATION, TEAMS AND PROJECTS SCHEMA

The Creator can create its own organization and it automatically becomes the Organization Manager.

Any organization can include several Teams created by the Organization Manager, which can invite any user in its own Teams.

Any Team has a Team Manager that can be nominated by the Organization Manager (by default the Organization Manager is also the Team Manager). At any invitation a request is sent to the specific user via mail and must be accepted.

The Team Manager can invite additional users and manage the projects and related content shared in a specific Team together with the Team Members.

In the first version of the Content Manager, the Organizations and Teams are visualized in the main section of the Content Management UI as separated Content Repositories, in which the user can share content with other users or visualize the already shared content.

Additional features in the shared environment will be implemented in the next version of the Content Management Tool.

6.2.1.1 Architecture

The Content Management tool has been implemented as a sub-app of the DAFNE+ Platform. It consists of a three-layer architecture:

- **UI Layer**, includes a web interface that allows content creators to manage their own contents
- **Service Layer**, provides the business logic, including the content management features, the contribution and revenue mechanisms, the integration with the Blockchain Realm and the APIs for external integration
- **Storage Layer**, provides the management of the content metadata and the media assets storage

Figure 22 below shows the high-level picture of the Content Management Tool architecture.

FIGURE 22: CONTENT MANAGEMENT TOOL ARCHITECTURE

UI Layer

The User Interface (UI) Layer is the presentation layer of the Content Management Tool. This Layer was implemented using REACT framework [15] and represents the entry points for the users. All the main features implemented within the tool are available through specific sections in the User Interface. Each section is described in this document.

Service Layer

The Service Layer implements the business logic of the Content Management Tool and provides the interfaces, based on REST APIs, for integrating both the UI Layer and the external applications of the DAFNE+ Platform (e.g., NFT Marketplace and Content Creation Tools).

This layer was implemented using NodeJS [16] and Express.js [17] and is integrated with the Identity Manager for managing the authentication and the authorization mechanisms of the DAFNE+ Platform.

Storage Layer

The Storage Layer manages all the data necessary for the implementation of Content Management services, and for ensuring the persistency of the media assets. It includes a NoSQL database (MongoDB [18]) for the storage of the application data, including metadata of the media assets and an interface for storing the media asset itself on the IPFS [19] infrastructure.

IPFS, as described in D2.1, is a modular suite of protocols for organizing and transferring data, designed from the ground up with the principles of content addressing and peer-to-peer networking. Thanks to main characteristics of IPFS, resilience, reliability and deduplication, it can be considered one of the best choices for addressing the storage of media assets linked to NFTs.

6.2.1.2 Specifications and interfaces

Import Content

The Import Content method allows to import any kind of media asset into the Content Management tool. It could be a media file or an external URL.

The content created within the creation tool can be imported in the Content Management and registered within the Blockchain Realm.

This important step allows to manage the content in a private environment (the creator one) adding a specific smart contract linked to the content. This smart contract is able to track the ownership of the content as well as to define contributors and revenue mechanisms.

Get Contents

The Get Contents method allows to retrieve the list of contents for a specific user.

Get Content Detail

The Get Content Detail method allows to retrieve all the information of a specific content, including information about smart contracts and contributors.

Update Content

The Update content method allows to interact with the content, updating its information. This method is important for registering all the activities related to the content such as:

- Contributors and revenue definition
- NFT creation
- NFT sale and revenue distribution

Table 3 reports the APIs implemented for integrating the Content Management Tool with other DAFNE+ components and services.

TABLE 3: CONTENT MANAGEMENT TOOL APIS

Name	Url	Method	Parameters	Responses
Import Content	/api/contents	POST	In body:	Success (200) Error (401) Unauthorized - <i>String</i> Error (500)

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

				Internal Server Error - <i>String</i>
Import External Content (URL)	/api/contents/url	POST	In body:	Success (200) Error (401) Unauthorized - <i>String</i> Error (500) Internal Server Error - <i>String</i>
Get Contents	/api/contents	GET	None	Success (200) Error (401) Unauthorized - <i>String</i> Error (500) Internal Server Error - <i>String</i>
Get Content Details	/api/contents/{id}	GET	In <u>params</u> : <i>id - String</i>	Success (200) Error (401) Unauthorized - <i>String</i> Error (500) Internal Server Error - <i>String</i>

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

Update Content	/api/contents/	PATCH	In <u>body</u> :	Success (200) Error (401) Unauthorized - <i>String</i> Error (500) Internal Server Error - <i>String</i>
----------------	----------------	-------	------------------	--

6.2.1.3 GUI sections

Content List

Figure 23 shows the section of the Content Management in which the Creator can visualize the list of imported contents.

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

FIGURE 23: CONTENT MANAGEMENT GUI - CONTENT LIST

Import Content

Figure 24 shows the section of the Content Management in which the Creator can import a new content by uploading a file.

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

FIGURE 24: CONTENT MANAGEMENT GUI – IMPORT CONTENT

Add/Edit Contributors

Figure 25, Figure 26, and Figure 27 show the section of the Content Management in which the Creator can manage the revenue sharing and contributors.

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

FIGURE 25: CONTENT MANAGEMENT GUI - ADD/EDIT CONTRIBUTORS

FIGURE 26: CONTENT MANAGEMENT GUI - METAMASK INTEGRATION

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

FIGURE 27: CONTENT MANAGEMENT GUI - CONTRIBUTORS LIST AND REVENUE SHARING

Organizations, Teams and Projects

Figure 28, Figure 29, Figure 30, Figure 31 and Figure 32 show the Organization and Teams Management section.

FIGURE 28: CONTENT MANAGEMENT GUI - NEW ORGANIZATION

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

FIGURE 29: CONTENT MANAGEMENT GUI - ORGANIZATION LIST

FIGURE 30: CONTENT MANAGEMENT GUI - NEW TEAM

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

FIGURE 31: CONTENT MANAGEMENT GUI - NEW TEAM MEMBER

FIGURE 32: CONTENT MANAGEMENT GUI - MY TEAMS AND SHARED CONTENTS

6.2.1.4 Integration and deployment guidelines

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101061548

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

As described in Ch. 3.2.2, the deployment process foresees using Docker containers. The use of Docker ensures not only an easy deployment process and total portability of the solution, but also a high level of scalability of the released applications.

Hardware

OS: Linux Host

RAM: > 4GB

Disk: > 100GB

Software

Docker > 24.0

Docker Compose > v2.21

Backend

Edit .env file, replacing the following properties:

```
SERVER_CONTENT_MANAGEMENT_PORT_BASE_PATH_SWAGGER=<swagger_api_url>  
SERVER_CONTENT_MANAGEMENT_PORT_DB_HOST=<db_url>  
SERVER_CONTENT_MANAGEMENT_MASTER_API_URL=<master_app_url>  
SERVER_CONTENT_MANAGEMENT_KUBO_NODE=<ipfs_node_url>  
SERVER_CONTENT_MANAGEMENT_BLOCKCHAIN_DEPLOY_CONTRACT_ENDPOINT_URL=<blockchain_realm_url>
```

Launch Docker Compose

```
$ docker-compose up -d
```

Frontend

Edit .env file, replacing the following properties:

```
SUB_APP_CONTENT_MANAGEMENT_API_URL=<backend_api_url>  
SUB_APP_CONTENT_MANAGEMENT_IPFS_GATEWAY=<ipfs_gateway>
```


D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

```
Launch Docker Compose
```

```
$ docker-compose up -d
```

6.2.2 Tools Catalogue

The Tools Catalogue lists the Dafne+ Platform internal and external toolset. The internal toolset includes the Automatic Art Generator, Style Transfer, NFT Content Analysis, 3D Object Reconstruction, 3D Human Pose Reconstruction, Virtual Avatar Personalisation and WebPD. RAVE v2, nn-, Dicy2, Spat, Soundworks and CoMo are part of the external toolset.

The tools are listed as cards displaying metadata from the Tools Catalogue API.

The user can select a tool and download it as a standalone application or use the Content Creation integrated in the platform to create artistic content.

6.2.2.1 Architecture

The Tools Catalogue is implemented as a sub-application of the DAFNE+ platform. Its architecture is made of two main components:

- Tools Catalogue Backend for storing data and exposing its API.
- Tools Catalogue Frontend to display data from its API and integrate it into the master application.

Tools Catalogue Backend

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

The Tools Catalogue Backend uses MongoDB [18] and the NestJS [20] framework to scaffold the Tools Catalogue REST API. The database and API apps are each contained into their own Docker containers. It enables CRUD operations to list, create, update and delete a tool item.

Tools Catalogue Frontend

The Tools Catalogue Frontend is implemented using Webpack 5.0, Typescript, Vue3 using the Composition API, Vue Router and a custom Git Typescript Interface to interact with Github and Gitlab APIs. It parses the metadata for each API endpoints defined in the Tools Catalog API to display it in the tools cards listing and detail pages. If a git repository url is specified in the tool api endpoint, the Tool Catalogue can display its README, releases, tags, branches and contributors directly into the DAFNE+ platform.

6.2.2.2 Specifications and interfaces

The purpose of the Tools Catalogue API is to list all the API endpoints of the DAFNE+ platform toolset. These endpoints are then fetched by the Tools Catalogue Frontend application and metadata is parsed accordingly.

Tools Catalogue API

The Tools Catalogue OpenAPI documentation is available here:

https://gitlab.com/dafne-plus/tools/tools-catalogue/tools-catalogue-backend/-/blob/main/swagger_output.json

Get Tool

Allows to retrieve the list of all the tools API endpoints.

Get Tool Detail

Allows to retrieve the information of a specific tool given its id.

Create Tool

Allows to create a tool item by providing its name and endpoint url.

Update Tool

Allows to update a specific tool information given its id, primarily its API endpoint url.

Delete Tool Detail

Allows to delete the information of a specific tool given its id.

The following table details the Tools Catalogue API:

Name	Url	Method	Parameters	Responses
Create Tool	/api/tools	POST	In body: <i>name - String</i> <i>api_url - String</i>	Success (201) Error (403) Unauthorized - <i>String</i> Error (422) Bad Request - <i>String</i>

Get Tools	/api/tools	GET	None	Success (200) Error (403) Unauthorized - <i>String</i>
Get Tool Details	/api/tools/{id}	GET	In <u>body</u> : id - <i>String</i>	Success (200) Error (403) Unauthorized - <i>String</i> Error (404) Resource not found - <i>String</i>
Update Tool	/api/tools/ {id}	PATCH	In <u>body</u> : name - <i>String</i> api_url - <i>String</i>	Success (200) Error (403) Unauthorized - <i>String</i> Error (404) Resource not found - <i>String</i> Error (422) Bad Request - <i>String</i>

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

DeleteTool	/api/tools/ {id}	DELETE	In <u>body</u> : id - <i>String</i>	Success (200) Error (403) Unauthorized - <i>String</i> Error (404) Ressource not found - <i>String</i>
------------	------------------	--------	--	--

Each tool must expose its own metadata through its REST API to display it in the listing cards and the detail pages. The list of fields to expose through the API are listed here: https://gitlab.com/dafne-plus/tools/tools-catalogue/tools-catalogue-frontend/-/blob/main/swagger_output.json?ref_type=heads

Here is a list of the common fields for each tool metadata:

- **name** (required, string)
- **description** (string)
- **image_thumbnail** (string, link to the tool image thumbnail displayed in cards)
- **author** (string)
- **version** (string)
- **download_url** (string, used to download the tool executable)
- **git_repository_url** (string, used to retrieve metadata from the tool git repository if it exists)
- **git_vendor** (string, either “github” or “gitlab”)
- **app_url** (string, url of the tool if it can be embedded as a web application)

GUI Sections

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101061548

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

Tools List

FIGURE 33: TOOLS CATALOGUE GUI - TOOL LIST

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

Tool Detail

The screenshot shows the 'Tool Detail' page for 'WebPd' in the 'DAFNE+ Tools Catalogue'. The page has a dark theme with pink and purple accents. At the top left, there is a 'Back' button. The title 'WebPd' is displayed in a large, pixelated font. Below the title, a description states: 'WebPd is a highly modular web audio programming toolkit inspired by Pure Data'. To the right, the author is listed as 'Sebastien Piquemal' and the version as '1.0.0'. The main content area is divided into two columns of information:

- Repository:** <https://github.com/sebpiq/WebPd>
- Owner:** sebpiq
- Branches:**
 - develop
 - main
- Contributors:** A row of seven small circular profile icons.
- Releases:** No releases yet.
- Tags:**
 - v1.0.0-alpha.3
 - v1.0.0-alpha.2
 - v1.0.0-alpha.1
 - v0.3.1
 - v0.3.0
 - v0.2.2
 - v0.2.1
 - v0.2

FIGURE 34: TOOLS CATALOGUE GUI - TOOL DETAIL

FIGURE 35: TOOLS CATALOGUE GUI - TOOL DOCUMENTATION

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

6.2.2.3 Integration and deployment guidelines

The Tools Catalogue Backend and Frontend applications are both dockerized, here are the steps to install and run the Docker containers.

Tools Catalogue Backend

To start the project, create an .env file at the root of the project with the following configurations.

```
APP_PORT=3000
```

```
MONGODB_URL=mongodb://mongodb:27017/Tool
```

Then start the Docker containers:

```
docker-compose up --build -d
```

Tools Catalogue Frontend

To start the project, create an .env file at the root of the project with the following configurations.

```
API_ENDPOINT_URL=http://localhost:300/api/tools
```

Then start the Docker containers by running the following command:

```
docker-compose up --build -d
```

6.2.3 Supporting tools - FAQ and Chat

This section describes the integration of supporting tools, specifically the Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) and Chat functionalities within the platform.

6.2.3.1 FAQ page

The FAQ page plays an important role in providing users with valuable information and assistance. It is designed to address common queries in the following key areas:

- General knowledge: Users can access information about DAOs, NFTs, blockchain, smart contracts and related concepts, fostering understanding within the community.
- Project specific questions: General inquiries about the project, its objectives, and expected outcomes are answered, promoting transparency and engagement.
- DAO Platform Queries: Users can find information on the project's DAO platform, including usage guidelines, legal considerations, and the available tools.

The FAQ page goes beyond text-based responses, it incorporates instructional videos to offer step-by-step guidance on utilizing the platform. Feedback from beta users will continuously improve and expand the FAQ, ensuring its relevance and effectiveness. Furthermore, the FAQ will be seamlessly integrated with the chat functionality, providing a comprehensive community support ecosystem.

6.2.3.2 Chat possibilities

The integration of a chat system is essential for enhancing user support and engagement. These are the three approaches available for chat integration:

- **Developing from Scratch:** Building a custom chat system from the ground up offers complete customization but may require significant development resources and time.
- **Framework Utilization:** Utilizing existing frameworks for chat development strikes a balance between customization and efficiency, with numerous frameworks available for integration.
- **Embedding Existing Chat Platforms:** Embedding popular chat platforms, such as Discord, Slack, or others, offers a quick and user-friendly solution that benefits from existing user bases.

To make an informed decision regarding the chat integration, a comprehensive comparative analysis of various options has been conducted. This comparison considered the unique characteristics and suitability of each option, weighing their respective pros and cons. Below, you will find the summary table highlighting the key factors influencing our choice of chat platform for the project.

TABLE 4: CHAT SOLUTIONS COMPARISON

SOLUTION	PROS	CONS
Discord	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User friendly interface • Large user base & many features • Bots to automate tasks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not fully decentralized • Limited customization options and brandin • May not be suitable for privacy-focused communities
Rocket.chat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fully customizable and open-source, • Provides support for video and audio calls 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires more technical expertise to set up • Smaller user base compared to other solutions,

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can be self-hosted 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires additional plugins for some functionalities
Matrix	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decentralized and end-to-end encryption • Support for video and audio calls • Can integrate with different chat clients 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires more technical expertise to set up • The user interface is not as user-friendly as others • Less established than other solutions,
Slack	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User-Friendly Interface • Third-Party Integrations: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costs Can Increase with Premium Features • Data Retention Policy
Own Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides full control over the functionality • Can be fully decentralized 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires more technical expertise and development time • More expensive to develop and maintain • Smaller user base, difficult to attract users

Table 4 provides a clear overview of the strengths and considerations for each option, ultimately guiding the selection. After thorough analysis, Discord has been selected as the primary chat platform for our project.

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Discord offers a wealth of features, user-friendliness, and widespread adoption, aligning perfectly with our project’s objectives and the needs of our community.

6.2.3.3 Integration and deployment

The integration of the chat functionality on the FAQ is done by using the WidgetBot tool from Discord. This tool creates a script that adds a fixed icon at the bottom of the page, enabling users to initiate chat sessions with ease, promoting user engagement and support. Additionally, deployment considerations, including the discord server configurations and user access, will be addressed to ensure a smooth and reliable experience for DANFE + community.

FIGURE 36: CHAT PLUGIN BUTTON – DISCORD ICON

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FIGURE 37: CHAT PLUGIN DISPLAYED

6.2.4 GIT and Version Management

The DAFNE+ use-cases foresee the possibility for users to produce and manage different versions of a same DAFNE+ asset. A first version of the Version manager was designed, released and tested in the framework of the IRCAM Forum platform for the management of *project* versions (in the IRCAM Forum terminology) or *component* versions (in the DAFNE+ terminology) i.e. successive releases of creative software tools.

A version combines one or several files (*assets* in the Forum terminology) and has the following properties:

- **Version name** (Preferred version number, semver recommended)
- **Description** (Indication of platform or format compatibility, displayed below name)
- **Version number** (Semantic version management preferred <https://semver.org>; Displayed in version title)

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

- **Release date**, In YYYY/MM/DD format, Displayed in version title

- **Status**

- o Draft
- o Public (default)
- o Archived

A version editing form allows the user to create, modify or delete a version, change the version display order and select a version to highlight. It is activated by clicking on the edit button (pencil icon) of the display interface.

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

Spat

Project

Places - Ircam Max lib Informatique musicale - MaxMSP Real time Spatialisation Technologies Ircam Free

Spat is a software suite for spatialization of sound signals in real-time intended for musical creation, postproduction, and live performances.

Versions

v5.3.1 2023-05-02

macOS, Windows

[Notes de version](#)

Spat-5.3.1-macos-02-05-2023.dmg (1.43 GB)

from 2023/02/16: 1650 [Download](#)

Spat-5.3.1-win64-02-05-2023.zip (1.33 GB)

from 2023/02/16: 902 [Download](#)

Other versions

v5.3.0 - 2023-03-29

macOS, Windows

[Notes de version](#)

v5.2.9 - 2022-09-27

macOS, Windows

[Notes de version](#)

Spat (or Spatialisateur in French) is a real-time spatial audio processor that allows composers, sound artists, performers, and sound engineers to control the localization of sound sources in 3D auditory spaces. In addition, Spat provides a powerful reverberation engine that can be applied to real and virtual auditory spaces.

FIGURE 38: EXAMPLE OF VERSIONS DISPLAY INTERFACE IN IRCAM FORUM

In addition to the management of versions based on assets downloaded manually by the user into the content management system, IRCAM also developed a Git repository manager, which is embedded into the Tools Catalogue and that can act as an API interface to retrieve metadata from Github and Gitlab repositories.

6.3 Additional tools

In addition to the DAFNE+ platform tools, some complimentary tools will be adopted and deployed to support the platform and the project tasks. These tools include Matomo [21] and Discourse [22], described below.

6.3.1 Matomo

To support the system evaluation and data analysis (T5.4) efforts, we will adopt the open-source web analytics platform. This tool will help with the evaluation and monitoring of the use case pilots and will inform the different design and development phases. The automatic collection of metrics will help to assess and optimize our Key Performance Indicators.

6.3.2 Discourse

There is a great need of a tool that DAFNE+ platform users will use to propose and discuss proposals raised during the Use Case refinement process (T2.3) as well as for the Revenue Model development (T6.3). The most widely adopted technology for this purpose in the blockchain NFT communities is discourse, an **open-source forum with voting capabilities**. Thus, this technology will be adopted and deployed along DAFNE+ platform to enable the governance processes of the platform, as introduced in D2.2 and D6.3.

6.4 Content Creation Tools

In the first version of the DAFNE+ platform, the following Content Creation Tools were successfully integrated:

- Virtual Avatar
- Style Transfer
- 3d Pose Estimation
- 3d Object Reconstruction

Below the integration and deployment guidelines for the Content Creation Tools on the DAFNE+ Platform.

6.4.1 Object Reconstruction Tool Backend

6.4.1.1 Introduction

This is the backend service of the DAFNE+ 3D object reconstruction tool, responsible for generating a 3D object in voxel representation given a number of images of the object taken from different angles / viewpoints. The tool has been tested with an input of at least 1 image to a maximum of 30 images. The more images added, the better the fidelity of the generated object.

6.4.1.2 Test and Deploy

To deploy the service run:

```
docker-compose up
```

The application is currently listening at: <http://localhost:5000>.

To test the service download the test_images folder and the bash test_object.sh script and then run:

```
./test_object IP_ADDRESS_URL
```

IP_ADDRESS_URL can be <http://localhost:5000> or the deployed address. A successful test produces the message "Test succeeded with correct output!", while a failed test produced the message "Test failed!".

6.4.1.3 Authors and acknowledgment

CERTH

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

6.4.1.4 License

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6.4.1.5 Current Version

Version: 1.1.0

6.4.2 3D Object Reconstruction Frontend

6.4.2.1 Introduction

This is the frontend service of the 3D object reconstruction tool that allows the user to upload a set of images of an object captured from different viewpoints and outputs a voxelized 3D object. The 3D object is created either in .STL or in .OBJ format and it can be downloaded locally or uploaded to the DAFNE+ platform.

6.4.2.2 Deploy

To deploy the application, enter the deploy folder and run docker compose:

```
cd deploy
docker-compose up --build
```

To deploy the application from the docker hub, enter the deploy_from_hub folder and run docker compose:

```
cd deploy_from_hub
docker-compose up
```

The application is currently listening at: <http://localhost:3000>.

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

6.4.2.3 Test in development mode

To test the app in development mode, you have to create a .env file in the root directory and define the CONTENT_MANAGEMENT_URL and the OBJECT_RECONSTRUCTION_BACKEND_URL as:

```
SUB_APP_OBJECT_RECONSTRUCTION_CONTENT_MANAGEMENT_URL=http://dafneplus.northeurope.cloudapp.azure.com/api-url-content-management/api/contents/  
SUB_APP_OBJECT_RECONSTRUCTION_BACKEND_URL=http://dafne-production.northeurope.cloudapp.azure.com:7005/
```

6.4.2.4 Authors and acknowledgment

CERTH

6.4.2.5 License

Please see LICENSE.md file for the respective licence.

6.4.2.6 Current Version

Version: 1.2.0

6.4.3 Pose estimation Tool Backend

6.4.3.1 Introduction

This is the backend service of the DAFNE+ 3D pose estimation tool, responsible for generating 3D human poses given a video sequence of humans performing actions.

6.4.3.2 Test and Deploy

To deploy the service run:

```
docker-compose up
```


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The application is currently listening at: <http://localhost:5000>.

6.4.3.3 Authors and acknowledgment

CERTH

6.4.3.4 License

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6.4.3.5 Current Version

Version: 1.0.0

6.4.4 3D Pose Estimation Frontend

6.4.4.1 Introduction

This is the frontend service of the 3D pose estimation tool that allows the user to upload a video sequence of 1 or more people performing actions and outputs the 3D poses of these people as avatar model shapes and motions. The 3D poses of each person are stored in a .FBX format and the poses of all people in the scene are zipped in a .zip file that can be downloaded locally or uploaded to the DAFNE+ platform.

6.4.4.2 Deploy

To deploy the application, enter the deploy folder and run docker compose:

```
cd deploy
docker-compose up --build
```


D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

To deploy the application from the docker hub, enter the *deploy_from_hub* folder and run docker compose:

```
cd deploy_from_hub
docker-compose up
```

The application is currently listening at: <http://localhost:3000>.

6.4.4.3 Test in development mode

To test the app in development mode, you have to create a .env file in the root directory and define the CONTENT_MANAGEMENT_URL and the POSE_ESTIMATION_BACKEND_URL as:

```
SUB_APP_POSE_ESTIMATION_CONTENT_MANAGEMENT_URL=http://dafneplus.northeurope.cloudapp.azure.com/api-url-content-management/api/contents/
SUB_APP_POSE_ESTIMATION_BACKEND_URL=http://dafne-production.northeurope.cloudapp.azure.com:7005/
```

In addition, the maximum upload file size should also be defined (in MB) as the size of the generated file can take high values.

```
SUB_APP_POSE_ESTIMATION_MAX_UPLOAD_SIZE=100
```

6.4.4.4 Authors and acknowledgment

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6.4.4.5 License

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6.4.4.6 Current Version

Version: 1.0.0

6.4.5 Style transfer tool - Backend

This repository holds the guidance for executing and deploying an image that encompasses the style transfer tool.

To test this module run:

```
docker-compose up
```

6.4.6 Style transfer tool – UI

6.4.6.1 Environmental Parameters

The services that are executed as containers, thus forming the style transfer ui receive their configurations from a .env file located in the deployment folder. In the following table, the environmental parameters that are necessary for the configuration and deployment of the style transfer ui are recorded and described.

Docker and Internal Services

TABLE 5: STYLE TRANSFER TOOL ENVIRONMENT VARIABLES

Environment Variable	Tag	Description
REACT_APP_SUB_APP_STYLE_TRANSFER_API	backend	API base HTTP url
REACT_APP_SUB_APP_STYLE_TRANSFER_DAFNE_PLUS_PLATFORM	backend	Dafneplus base HTTP url

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

REACT_APP_SUB_APP_CONTENT_MANAGEMENT	backend	DAFNE+ Content Management API URL
--------------------------------------	---------	-----------------------------------

6.4.6.2 Deployment

Create a .env file with the environment variables as described in the section above, and run:

```
docker compose up -d
```

6.4.7 Virtual Avatar Personalization Frontend

6.4.7.1 Introduction

This is the virtual avatar personalization application that allows the user to create a customized avatar with specific choices on skin color, hair style and color and clothes (i.e., shirt, trousers and shoes). The created 3D avatar, along with the corresponding textures, can be downloaded locally or uploaded to the DAFNE+ platform as a compressed file (.zip).

6.4.7.2 Deploy

To deploy the application locally, enter the deploy folder and run docker compose:

```
cd deploy
docker-compose up --build
```

To deploy the application from the docker hub, enter the *deploy_from_hub* folder and run docker compose:

```
cd deploy_from_hub
docker-compose up
```

The application is currently listening at: <http://localhost:3000>.

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

6.4.7.3 Test in development mode

To test the app in development mode, you have to create a .env file in the root directory and define the CONTENT_MANAGEMENT_URL as:

```
SUB_APP_VIRTUAL_AVATAR_CONTENT_MANAGEMENT_URL=http://dafneplus.northeurope.cloudapp.azure.com/api-url-content-management/api/contents/
```

6.4.7.4 Authors and acknowledgment

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6.4.7.5 License

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6.4.7.6 Current Version

Version: 1.2.0

6.5 DAFNE+ Platform First Release

The first version of the DAFNE+ Platform is officially available at <https://dafneplus.eng.it> and it includes:

- Master App with authentication, registration and user profile management
- Content Management Tool
- Tools Catalogue
- 4 Content Creation Tools (Style Transfer, Virtual Avatar, 3d Pose Estimation Tool, 3d Object Reconstruction Tool)
- NFT Content Analysis service (only APIs)
- NFT Marketplace
- Integration Layer
- Blockchain Realm and NFT Tool

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

- IPFS Storage

In order to perform a User Acceptance Test of the DAFNE+ Platform, a test book was prepared and will be shared among the partners of the consortium and external users for the validation of the platform.

Below the template of the testbook.

Content-Management						
Number	Module	Acceptance Requirement	Test Result			Notes
			Date	Accept	Reject	
1	Contents	<u>Create Content (Metamask wallet not connected):</u> - The user try to add content - The system prevents the operation and shows the message: "please connect to MetaMask."				

FIGURE 39: TEST BOOK TEMPLATE FOR USER ACCEPTANCE TEST

7 Conclusion

Starting from the user requirements, technical specifications and architecture described in WP2 the DAFNE+ Platform Applications were developed and integrated in the overall DAFNE+ Platform.

The DAFNE+ Platform is a Multi-Layer and Multi-Application platform which includes both backend and frontend components.

In the context of T4.4 and T4.5 activities, mainly reported in this document, the End-User Applications development and design was described and more in detail: Content Management Tool, Tools Catalogue and Supporting Tool (Chat & FAQ).

In addition, the DAFNE+ Platform includes an Identity Management and Profile tool, based on KeyCloak and Integration Layer built using Kong.

The development of DAFNE+ Platform applications was entrusted to multiple teams, partners of the consortium, that need to work independently for implementing and releasing specific features of the platform itself. For this reason, in order to facilitate the development, integration and deployment of all the applications, the Micro Frontend approach was adopted by the consortium.

The integration phase consisted of the integration of all the end-user applications, included the Content Creation Tools, released in WP3 and Blockchain-based applications (like NFT Marketplace) released within the Task T4.1, T4.2 and T4.3.

At the end of this integration phase, the first DAFNE+ Platform was officially released and will be tested and evaluated within the first round of pilot.

At the end of the first validation phase, the DAFNE+ Platform will be enriched and improved following the feedback came out from the users and implementing the second wave of requirements as described in D2.1.

8 References

- [1] <https://micro-frontends.org>
- [2] <https://webpack.js.org/concepts/module-federation/>
- [3] <https://raz-levy.medium.com/communicating-between-micro-frontends-using-custom-events-in-react-js-e3dab0571edb>
- [4] <https://swagger.io/specification/>
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- [17] <https://nodejs.org/>
- [18] <https://expressjs.com>
- [19] <https://www.mongodb.com/>
- [20] <https://ipfs.tech>
- [21] <https://nestjs.com>
- [22] <https://matomo.org>

D4.2 – Report on platform specifications, development and provision and APIs for third party integration

[23] <https://discourse.org>

